

PMASynRM system-level NVH model with eccentricity

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Abstract—This paper presents a high-fidelity system-level vibration model for a permanent-magnet assisted synchronous reluctance machine that is able to capture static and dynamic eccentricity effects. The procedure of extracting finite-element data from a series of magnetostatic analyses that include rotor displacement is presented. Afterwards, the flux-linkage state variable system-level model that uses the previous data is developed. Subsequently, the vibration-synthesis method that includes the additional time and space eccentricity-induced force harmonics is discussed and vibration response of the system-level model is presented and compared to the non-eccentric case. Additionally, the effect of different eccentricity orbits on the unbalance magnetic pull force is exemplified.

Index Terms—PMASynRM, system-level model, static eccentricity, dynamic eccentricity, NVH, vibration synthesis;

I. INTRODUCTION

The acceleration in automotive electrification, for both traction and auxiliary applications, brings ever-increasing Noise, Vibration and Harshness (NVH) target requirements. The permanent magnet synchronous machine (PMSM) is the market leader in these segments due to its superior efficiency and power density.

Advanced multi-physics simulation techniques enhance the capabilities of the R&D engineer to investigate and troubleshoot PMSM NVH issues early in the design stage. The traditional NVH design process proceeds in a waterfall configuration, where first the 2D/3D electromagnetic finite element (FE) analysis is conducted and then the vibro-acoustic analysis, where the loads are the electromagnetic forces obtained from the previous step [1]. This process is time-consuming if a wide current or torque/speed range has to be analyzed. Boesing [2] proposes a faster simulation method that gives more insight into the cause-effect relationship of electrical machine NVH issue called the vibration-synthesis. This method efficiently synthesizes the vibrations caused by the air-gap force and can be applied to electric drive system-level models for fast time-domain NVH simulation [3],[4].

In this paper, the system-level model is extended in order to include machine axial symmetric eccentricity effects. Eccentricity is one of the common faults in electric drives and introduces additional time and space air-gap force orders together with the unbalanced magnetic pull (UMP) force that can have a major effect on the structural and air-borne noise. The advantage of using a system-level approach over a coupled

magneto-mechanical FE approach [1], [5] is that the computationally intensive FE simulation are done once in order to build the reduced-order models, thus saving computational effort without compromising accuracy [6]. This PMSM system-level model that includes eccentricity can be easily coupled with an electrical machine multi-body dynamics model [7] and can be used for rapid control algorithm development.

Werner [8] distinguishes between three main types of eccentricity: eccentricity of rotor mass, magnetic eccentricity and bent rotor deflection. The related causes can be residual unbalance of the rotor, bearing clearance and misalignment, and tolerances caused by the manufacturing process leading to an eccentric rotor core. These faults can lead to static eccentricity (SE) where the rotor geometric axis is the same as the rotation axis but differs from the stator geometric axis (Figure 1a) and dynamic eccentricity (DE) where the stator geometric axis is the same as the rotation axis but differs from the rotor geometric axis (Figure 1b). Additionally, rotor tilt (axial asymmetry) can be present [9] but this is not discussed in the current paper.

II. PMASynRM ELECTROMAGNETIC SYSTEM-LEVEL MODEL WITH ECCENTRICITY

A. Extracting data from a FE analysis with eccentricity effects

As a result of the eccentricity-induced geometrical asymmetries the full machine model has to be used for the FE analysis. The machine under study is a 6 poles Permanent Magnet Assisted Synchronous Reluctance Machine (PMASynRM), with a 0.5mm air-gap, used for light traction applications [10] with the cross-section presented in Figure 1 (c).

In order to construct the system-level model a series of magnetostatic FE simulations are performed that sweep through the current in the dq frame (i_{dq}), rotor position (θ_e) and x, y rotor displacement. The machine configuration permits an electrical rotor position symmetry of 180 degrees and an azimuthal rotor displacement symmetry, as mentioned in [11].

The parameters extracted are: the flux-linkages $\lambda_{dq}(i_d, i_q, x, y, \theta_e)$, electromagnetic torque computed using the nodal force approach $T_{em}(i_d, i_q, x, y, \theta_e)$, UMP computed through the rotor nodal force summation in the $x-y$ direction $UMP_{x,y}(i_d, i_q, x, y, \theta_e)$ and the air-gap radial and tangential flux densities $B_{rad,tan}(i_d, i_q, x, y, \theta_e, \alpha)$, where α is the air-gap position.

Fig. 1. SE (a), DE (b), where rotation sequence (1 → 2 → 3 → 4 → 1) are illustrated. (c) represents the studied PMASynRM mesh with 20% SE where the asymmetric air-gap is visible.

B. Flux-linkage state variable system-level model

There are two main approaches for building the system-level model based on look-up table (LUT) data obtained from FE (Figure 2). The difference lies in the state variable used to solve the voltage equation: either current or flux-linkage [6]. A current state variable model that takes into account eccentricity is proposed in [7], while this paper proposes a flux-linkage state variable model.

The first required step in the flux-linkage LUT inversion is going from $\lambda_{dq}(i_d, i_q, x, y, \theta_e)$ to $i_{dq}(\lambda_d, \lambda_q, x, y, \theta_e)$. This can be accomplished through multiple methods, such as: polynomial surface fitting or solving the Taylor series expansion [6]. Afterwards, the voltage equation is solved through integration:

$$\begin{aligned} v_d &= Ri_d(\lambda_d, \lambda_q, x, y, \theta_e) + \frac{d\varphi_d}{dt} - \omega_e \lambda_q \text{ and} \\ v_d &= Ri_q(\lambda_d, \lambda_q, x, y, \theta_e) + \frac{q\varphi_d}{dt} + \omega_e \lambda_d, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_d &= \int (v_d - Ri_d(\lambda_d, \lambda_q, x, y, \theta_e) + \omega_e \lambda_q) dt \text{ and} \\ \varphi_q &= \int (v_q - Ri_q(\lambda_d, \lambda_q, x, y, \theta_e) - \omega_e \lambda_d) dt, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where v_{dq} are the phase voltages in the dq frame, R is the stator phase resistance and ω_e is the electrical rotor speed

Fig. 2. FE-extracted parameters for different x-y eccentricity values: dq -axis flux linkage (a,b) x-y UMP (c,d), electromagnetic torque (e) and radial flux density (f).

Fig. 3. Significant rotor position dependent force amplitude factors for $i_d = -60A$, $i_q = 100A$, $x = 0.1mm$, $y = 0.1mm$ where the SE-induced factors are present.

in electrical radians per second. Finally, the electromagnetic torque is obtained directly from the LUT with the dq obtained currents.

III. PMASYNRM SYSTEM-LEVEL VIBRATION MODEL WITH ECCENTRICITY

A. Spatially decomposed air-gap force

The radial and tangential air-gap force waves are computed using the Maxwell Stress Tensor from the FE-obtained flux densities. This force wave ($F_{rad,tan}(i_d, i_q, x, y, t, \alpha)$), where the rotor position (θ_e) is substituted with the time dependency (t) is distributed along the air-gap (α). Hence, the force can be expressed as a spatially decomposed superposition of the most important excitation shapes using the $cos - sin$ orthogonal basis[2]:

$$F_{sup}((i_d, i_q, x, y, t, \alpha)) = f_{DC}(i_d, i_q, x, y, t) + \sum_{m=1}^M (f_{cos,m}(i_d, i_q, x, y, t) \cos(m\alpha) + f_{sin,m}(i_d, i_q, x, y, t) \sin(m\alpha)), \quad (3)$$

where M is the total number of spatial harmonics, m is the spatial force order, and $f_{cos,m}$, $f_{sin,m}$ and f_{DC} are the temporal-dependent amplitude factors as exemplified in Figure 3. The time and space orders of the radial force wave for a non-eccentric PMSM that have a major contribution are [12]:

$$F_{rad[time,space]} \propto [2np, -2np \pm 6mp \pm kN_s], \quad (4)$$

where $n, m, k \in N$, p is the number of pole pairs and N_s is the number of stator slots, as exemplified in Figure 4 (c).

Fig. 4. Radial force density in time (a) and frequency (b) domain for $i_d = -20A$, $i_q = 80A$ for the non-eccentric case.

Fig. 5. Unitary force shapes mapping on the stator structural dynamics FE mesh

B. Vibration synthesis

The vibration synthesis uses the superposition of dynamics responses for each important excitation force shape component [2]. This is achieved by using a modal frequency response solution, where the excitation $F_{[I],shape}$ is a unitary force shape with energy conservation properties - the total energy per frequency line equal to 1 N [13]:

$$v_{[I],shape}(f) = H(f)F_{[I],shape}(f), \quad (5)$$

where $v_{[I],shape}(f)$ is the frequency response for each force shape excitation and $H(f)$ is the transfer function matrix obtained from modal analysis. Figure 5 shows the structural dynamics FE mesh loaded with these unitary forces with different shapes while Figure 6 shows the unitary frequency response where we can observe the contribution of each force shape to each structural mode. For example, in Figure 6 (a) we can observe that the radial force component f_{DC} has a strong effect at 8290 Hz which is linked to the breathing mode, whereas the eccentricity induced f_{cos5} and f_{sin5} components interact with 5th mode at 6840 Hz, as showed in Figure 6 (a,b).

The total response $v(f)$ is the superposition of all frequency responses scaled with the $cos - sin$ amplitude factors obtained in the previous subsection:

$$v(f) = v_{[I],DC}(f)f_{DC}(i_d, i_q, x, y, f) + \sum_{m=1}^M (v_{[I],cos_m}f_{cos,m}(i_d, i_q, x, y, f) + v_{[I],sin_m}f_{sin,m}(i_d, i_q, x, y, f)). \quad (6)$$

Figure 7 shows the vibration synthesis results, for the

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Unitary frequency responses (magnitude) at node \circ (Figure 5a) in radial (a) and tangential (b) direction.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. Run-up responses (magnitude, scaled) at node \circ in radial (a) and tangential (b) direction for the non-eccentric case where $id = -20A$, $iq = 80A$.

non-eccentric case, including both radial and tangential force components, with ideal sinusoidal current input in the radial and tangential direction.

IV. RESULTS FOR DIFFERENT ECCENTRICITY ORBITS

In order to test the simulation model different eccentricity orbits are imposed. These consist of an ideal SE, DE a combination of static and dynamic eccentricity and a typical orbit measurement obtained from a test campaign, as shown in Figure 8 (a). The difference in radial force harmonics between the different orbit scenarios are shown in Figure 8 (b-d), where the error between the non-eccentric and different eccentricity cases is computed as follows:

$$F_{rad,err[time,space]} = F_{rad,0Ecc[time,space]} - F_{rad,Ecc[time,space]}, \quad (7)$$

where the subscript $0Ecc$ represents the non-eccentric case and Ecc the eccentric one determined by the different orbit plots.

The newly eccentricity introduced time and space force harmonics can interact with different structural mode shapes

(a)

(b) $F_{rad,errSE[time,space]}$ (c) $F_{rad,errDE[time,space]}$ (d) $F_{rad,errTestBased[time,space]}$

Fig. 8. Simulated orbit plots (a) and difference between the time/space harmonic error (b-d) for $id = -20A$, $iq = 80A$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 9. Run-up responses (magnitude, scaled) at node \circ for the DE/test-based imposed eccentricity orbit in radial (a/c) and tangential (b/d) direction where $id = -20A$, $iq = 80A$.

relative to the non-eccentric case, leading to different air-borne NVH signatures. This is illustrated in Figure 9 where the run-up vibration results are showed for the DE and test-based orbit. Additional resonances due to the excitation of eccentricity-induced force factors occur for both orbits, whereas different harmonic order peaks can be observed between the two eccentricity orbits, where the difference is marked with a red ellipse.

As for the structure-born noise, this is mostly affected by the

Fig. 10. Time/frequency-domain UMPx (a/c) and UMPy (b/d) results for SE (red), DE (blue), SE+DE (green) and test-based (black) eccentricity orbits at $id = -20A$, $iq = 80A$.

torque ripple and the UMP, where different eccentricity orbits introduce different time harmonics, as exemplified in Figure 10. The harmonic difference between the different orbits are more significant compared to the radial and tangential air-gap forces. Here, the time-domain system-level results (full line) are compared to FE (dots), except for the test-based orbit because it was not possible to implement in the FE software.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper the detailed steps for system-level modeling of an eccentric PMASynRM used for NVH simulation is presented. These steps include: extracting electromagnetic LUTs from FE simulations with rotor eccentricity dependency (using symmetries), performing the vibration-synthesis process on the stator structure in order to extract the unitary force-responses and coupling it together at the system-level. Results for different types of eccentricity orbits are presented and the interaction between eccentricity, electromagnetic quantities and structure response are discussed, thus explaining their cause-effect relationship and emphasizing the importance of including the eccentricity effects early in the design stage in order to model both air-born and structure-born noise.

The next step is to couple the system-level model with a power electronics control unit and a multi-body dynamics model of the power-train that is able to capture non-linear

bearing and gear behavior in order to further expand on modeling the structure-born noise.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. Pellerey, V. Lanfranchi, and G. Friedrich, "Numerical simulations of rotor dynamic eccentricity effects on synchronous machine vibrations for full run up," in *2012 XXth International Conference on Electrical Machines*. IEEE, 2012, pp. 3008–3014.
- [2] M. Boesing, T. Schoenen, K. A. Kasper, and R. W. De Doncker, "Vibration synthesis for electrical machines based on force response superposition," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 46, no. 8, pp. 2986–2989, 2010.
- [3] M. Boesing, A. Hofmann, and R. De Doncker, "Universal acoustic modelling framework for electrical drives," *IET Power Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 693–699, 2015.
- [4] P. Kotter, O. Zirn, and K. Wegener, "Efficient noise-vibration-harshness modelling of servo-and traction drives," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 49, no. 21, pp. 330–338, 2016.
- [5] F. Lin, S. Zuo, and W. Deng, "Impact of rotor eccentricity on electromagnetic vibration and noise of permanent magnet synchronous motor," *Journal of Vibroengineering*, vol. 20, no. 2, 2018.
- [6] S. Ciceo, F. Chauvicourt, J. Gyselinck, and C. Martis, "A comparative study of system-level pmsm models with either current or flux-linkage state variables used for vibro-acoustic computation," in *2019 IEEE International Electric Machines & Drives Conference (IEMDC)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1881–1888.
- [7] M. Mohr, O. Biro, and F. Diwoy, "Consideration of rotor eccentricity effects in a multi body dynamics simulation using a finite element based circuit model approach," in *2014 International Conference on Electrical Machines (ICEM)*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 1523–1528.
- [8] U. Werner, "Analysis of active vibration reduction for soft mounted electrical machines based on a multibody model," *International Journal of Applied Mechanics*, vol. 8, no. 08, p. 1650085, 2016.
- [9] A. Tenhunen, T. Benedetti, T. Holopainen, and A. Arkkio, "Electromagnetic forces in cage induction motors with rotor eccentricity," in *IEEE International Electric Machines and Drives Conference, 2003. IEMDC'03.*, vol. 3. IEEE, 2003, pp. 1616–1622.
- [10] B. Varaticeanu, P. Minciunescu, and S. Matei, "Performance evaluation of permanent magnet assisted synchronous reluctance motor for micro electric vehicle," in *Advanced Microsystems for Automotive Applications 2015*. Springer, 2016, pp. 173–186.
- [11] M. Mohr, O. Bíró, A. Stermecki, and F. Diwoy, "An extended finite element based model approach for permanent magnet synchronous machines including rotor eccentricity," in *IECON 2013-39th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 2596–2601.
- [12] A. Andersson and T. Thiringer, "Electrical machine acoustic noise reduction based on rotor surface modifications," in *2016 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 1–7.
- [13] F. Chauvicourt, S. Ciceo, and H. Van der Auweraer, "On the use of vibration synthesis to ease electric machine powertrain design," in *2019 IEEE International Electric Machines & Drives Conference (IEMDC)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1118–1125.